

A BCool survey of stellar magnetic cycles: Appendices

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B Additional figures temporal analysis

In this appendix, we provide complete information on the application of the generalised Lomb-Scargle periodogram to the time series of longitudinal magnetic field data for all stars. In the case of HD 166435, we also provide the temporal analysis of the *TESS* light curves collected in 2020, 2021, and 2022. Finally, we include the results of the Gaussian process regression for all stars, showing the GP model overplotted on the B_l time series and the corner plots illustrating the posterior distributions of the GP hyperparameters (see Sect. 4.2 in the paper for more details).

C Additional figures Zeeman-Doppler imaging

We present the observed LSD Stokes V profiles together with their ZDI models. In each figure, we show the profiles for the different epochs in which we applied ZDI.

D Journal of observations

In this appendix we report the list of observations conducted between 2007 and 2022 with Narval, Neo-Narval, and ESPaDOnS. The observations were carried out as part of the BCool survey.

Figure B.1: Generalised Lomb-Scargle periodogram analysis for our stars. The power spectrum is shown as a green solid line and the window function as a green dashed line mirrored with respect to the x axis. The horizontal dashed, and dash-dot grey lines represent the 0.01% and 0.1% FAP threshold, respectively.

Figure B.2: Photometric light curves of HD 166435 for the 2020, 2021, and 2022 epochs. Left: *TESS* light curves. The data points with a quality factor flag different than zero are shown as red crosses and removed from the temporal analysis. Right: generalised Lomb-Scargle periodogram applied to the light curves. The format of the periodogram panels is the same as Fig. B.1.

Figure B.3: Time series of longitudinal magnetic field measurements for HD 56124 and posterior distribution of the GP regression. The format is the same as Fig. 2 in the paper.

Figure B.4: Time series of longitudinal magnetic field measurements for HD 73350 and posterior distribution of the GP regression. The format is the same as Fig. 2 in the paper.

Figure B.5: Time series of longitudinal magnetic field measurements for HD 76151 and posterior distribution of the GP regression. The format is the same as Fig. 2 in the paper. The rotation period scale is restricted to a maximum of 35 d for visualisation purposes, but the uniform prior encompassed the interval 1-50 d.

Figure B.6: Time series of longitudinal magnetic field measurements for HD 166435 and posterior distribution of the GP regression. The format is the same as Fig. 2 in the paper.

Figure B.7: Time series of longitudinal magnetic field measurements for HD 175726 and posterior distribution of the GP regression. The format is the same as Fig. 2 in the paper.

HD 9986

Figure C.1: Time series of Stokes V LSD profiles and the ZDI models for HD 9986. The observations are shown in grey and the models in red. The numbers on the right indicate the rotational cycle computed from Eq. 1 in the paper using the first observation of an epoch as reference date. The horizontal line represents the zero point of the profiles, which are shifted vertically based on their rotational phase for visualisation purposes.

HD 56124

Figure C.2: Time series of Stokes V LSD profiles and the ZDI models for HD 56124. The format is the same as Fig. C.1.

HD 73350

Figure C.3: Time series of Stokes V LSD profiles and the ZDI models for HD 73350. The format is the same as Fig. C.1.

HD 76151

Figure C.4: Time series of Stokes V LSD profiles and the ZDI models for HD 76151. The format is the same as Fig. C.1.

HD 166435

Figure C.5: Time series of Stokes V LSD profiles and the ZDI models for HD 166435. The format is the same as Fig. C.1.

HD 175726

Figure C.6: Time series of Stokes V LSD profiles and the ZDI models for HD 175726. The format is the same as Fig. C.1.

Table D.1: Observations of HD 9986. The columns are: (1 and 2) date and universal time of the observations, (3) rotational cycle of the observations found using Eq. 1 in the paper, (4) exposure time of a polarimetric sequence, (5) signal-to-noise ratio at 650 nm per polarimetric sequence, (6) RMS noise level of Stokes V signal in units of unpolarised continuum, (7) longitudinal magnetic field and formal error bar, (8) S -index and formal error bar.

Date	UT [hh:mm:ss]	n_{cyc}	t_{exp} [s]	S/N	σ_{LSD} [$10^{-5}I_c$]	B_ℓ [G]	S -index
2008							
Jan 19	18:05:05	0.00	4x800.0	364	9.1	1.20 ± 1.43	0.208 ± 0.013
Jan 21	18:12:30	0.10	4x900.0	672	4.1	0.32 ± 0.72	0.208 ± 0.006
Jan 22	18:06:46	0.14	4x900.0	472	6.8	0.40 ± 1.04	0.210 ± 0.009
Jan 23	18:12:35	0.19	4x900.0	543	5.8	-0.17 ± 0.94	0.210 ± 0.008
Jan 24	18:42:40	0.24	4x900.0	511	5.8	-0.06 ± 0.99	0.209 ± 0.007
Jan 25	18:17:39	0.29	4x900.0	548	5.4	-0.59 ± 0.91	0.209 ± 0.008
Jan 27	18:33:25	0.38	4x900.0	565	5.7	-0.21 ± 0.90	0.211 ± 0.008
Jan 28	18:56:29	0.43	4x900.0	683	4.5	0.26 ± 0.71	0.209 ± 0.006
Jan 29	18:46:08	0.48	4x900.0	631	4.6	0.51 ± 0.76	0.211 ± 0.006
Jan 31	18:43:48	0.57	4x900.0	607	4.7	0.46 ± 0.80	0.213 ± 0.007
Feb 02	18:48:27	0.67	4x900.0	657	5.0	0.75 ± 0.76	0.211 ± 0.007
Feb 05	18:25:14	0.81	4x900.0	587	5.6	0.37 ± 0.85	0.208 ± 0.007
Feb 06	18:26:19	0.86	4x900.0	581	4.8	-0.44 ± 0.84	0.208 ± 0.007
Feb 09	18:36:13	1.00	4x900.0	518	6.4	1.57 ± 0.99	0.209 ± 0.009
Feb 11	18:41:48	1.09	4x900.0	650	4.5	2.04 ± 0.77	0.208 ± 0.006
Feb 12	18:44:39	1.14	4x900.0	656	4.4	1.35 ± 0.76	0.208 ± 0.006
Feb 13	18:46:18	1.19	4x900.0	589	4.9	0.41 ± 0.85	0.207 ± 0.007
Feb 14	19:09:42	1.24	4x900.0	626	4.8	0.13 ± 0.77	0.207 ± 0.006
Feb 15	18:40:03	1.28	4x900.0	682	4.2	-2.13 ± 0.72	0.208 ± 0.006
Feb 16	18:50:50	1.33	4x900.0	649	4.4	-0.59 ± 0.76	0.209 ± 0.007
2010							
Sep 19	03:00:16	46.29	4x900.0	649	5.1	-0.24 ± 0.74	0.207 ± 0.006
Sep 21	23:11:40	46.42	4x900.0	577	5.8	-0.35 ± 0.88	0.208 ± 0.008
Sep 27	01:35:48	46.66	4x900.0	620	4.3	-0.05 ± 0.79	0.209 ± 0.007
Sep 29	01:42:03	46.76	4x900.0	607	4.6	-0.48 ± 0.81	0.210 ± 0.007
Oct 05	02:41:37	47.05	4x900.0	568	5.5	-1.38 ± 0.87	0.209 ± 0.008
Oct 06	01:04:38	47.09	4x900.0	461	6.9	-0.36 ± 1.12	0.210 ± 0.011
Oct 09	01:45:05	47.23	4x900.0	217	16.2	-0.63 ± 2.70	0.200 ± 0.026
Oct 14	24:05:03	47.52	4x900.0	767	3.9	0.78 ± 0.61	0.210 ± 0.005
Oct 15	23:57:02	47.56	4x900.0	607	4.8	0.12 ± 0.80	0.211 ± 0.007
2011							
Oct 04	00:35:19	64.35	4x900.0	695	4.5	-1.20 ± 0.71	0.204 ± 0.006
Oct 05	02:06:58	64.40	4x900.0	681	4.7	-2.01 ± 0.71	0.205 ± 0.006
Oct 06	01:48:03	64.45	4x900.0	744	4.2	-1.01 ± 0.65	0.204 ± 0.005
Oct 10	23:10:11	64.68	4x900.0	478	6.3	-0.59 ± 1.07	0.198 ± 0.010
Oct 11	23:15:54	64.73	4x225.0	17	...	...	...
Oct 13	22:12:16	64.82	4x900.0	699	4.2	1.14 ± 0.69	0.201 ± 0.006
Oct 15	02:21:29	64.88	4x900.0	688	4.4	-0.55 ± 0.74	0.202 ± 0.008
Oct 31	21:21:52	65.67	4x900.0	640	4.8	0.50 ± 0.78	0.205 ± 0.007
Nov 08	22:15:38	66.06	4x900.0	525	5.9	-0.35 ± 0.99	0.202 ± 0.009
Nov 10	23:34:29	66.15	4x900.0	394	8.2	-0.61 ± 1.32	0.195 ± 0.013
Nov 11	21:24:45	66.20	4x900.0	525	5.8	-1.41 ± 0.96	0.202 ± 0.009
2012							
Oct 09	23:02:41	82.04	4x900.0	278	11.3	-1.49 ± 1.93	0.204 ± 0.019
Oct 13	22:38:02	82.23	4x900.0	614	4.6	0.93 ± 0.78	0.208 ± 0.006
Oct 23	24:07:58	82.70	4x900.0	486	6.5	-1.35 ± 1.02	0.199 ± 0.009
Oct 28	22:55:15	82.94	4x225.0	436	...	...	...
Oct 29	22:46:11	82.99	4x900.0	674	4.7	-0.27 ± 0.72	0.205 ± 0.006
Oct 31	22:42:25	83.08	4x900.0	471	6.5	-1.59 ± 1.01	0.206 ± 0.008
Nov 06	22:36:49	83.37	4x1200.0	587	5.0	-0.49 ± 0.85	0.206 ± 0.007
Nov 12	23:02:30	83.65	4x900.0	481	6.7	-1.03 ± 1.03	0.197 ± 0.009
Nov 14	21:21:18	83.74	4x900.0	576	5.4	-0.87 ± 0.84	0.201 ± 0.007

Nov 19	20:53:33	83.98	4x900.0	535	5.7	-2.30 ± 0.91	0.204 ± 0.008
Nov 22	21:19:02	84.12	4x900.0	588	5.3	0.97 ± 0.82	0.208 ± 0.007
Dec 10	19:30:49	84.98	4x900.0	631	4.6	-0.70 ± 0.75	0.205 ± 0.006
Dec 11	19:43:43	85.02	4x900.0	581	5.5	-0.95 ± 0.83	0.204 ± 0.007
2013							
Sep 22	02:05:52	98.54	4x900.0	675	4.4	-0.49 ± 0.69	0.215 ± 0.006
2015							
Jan 05	18:26:26	120.92	4x900.0	592	5.1	0.36 ± 0.81	0.207 ± 0.007
Jan 07	18:27:30	121.02	4x900.0	642	4.8	-0.08 ± 0.75	0.204 ± 0.006
Jan 09	18:12:22	121.11	4x900.0	635	5.0	-0.19 ± 0.76	0.206 ± 0.006
2017							
Sep 26	24:16:21	168.25	4x900.0	379	8.0	-0.80 ± 1.35	0.209 ± 0.012
Sep 28	24:30:18	168.34	4x900.0	392	7.1	0.31 ± 1.24	0.211 ± 0.012
Sep 29	23:55:21	168.39	4x900.0	386	7.4	2.40 ± 1.30	0.212 ± 0.013
Oct 03	00:53:60	168.53	4x900.0	391	7.2	0.77 ± 1.24	0.214 ± 0.012
Oct 03	23:53:07	168.58	4x900.0	368	7.5	-0.78 ± 1.36	0.213 ± 0.013
Oct 04	23:46:45	168.63	4x900.0	310	10.1	-1.99 ± 1.64	0.217 ± 0.017
Oct 05	24:10:33	168.68	4x900.0	533	5.5	-0.49 ± 0.87	0.216 ± 0.007
Oct 06	23:39:16	168.72	4x900.0	477	5.8	-1.56 ± 1.00	0.216 ± 0.009
Oct 07	24:16:19	168.77	4x900.0	553	5.0	-0.71 ± 0.87	0.216 ± 0.007
Oct 08	24:12:48	168.82	4x900.0	485	5.7	2.46 ± 0.97	0.215 ± 0.009
Oct 10	01:11:44	168.87	4x900.0	457	6.3	1.73 ± 1.03	0.215 ± 0.009
Oct 11	01:49:35	168.92	4x900.0	529	5.2	3.33 ± 0.92	0.216 ± 0.008
Oct 12	01:55:19	168.96	4x900.0	494	5.4	2.73 ± 1.00	0.215 ± 0.009
Oct 12	23:52:10	169.01	4x900.0	441	6.9	1.86 ± 1.10	0.215 ± 0.010
Oct 13	23:57:29	169.06	4x900.0	482	6.5	2.84 ± 0.98	0.213 ± 0.009
2018							
Sep 18	24:30:00	185.22	4x900.0	516	6.4	1.82 ± 0.99	0.209 ± 0.010
Sep 20	01:20:03	185.27	4x900.0	499	6.4	0.57 ± 1.00	0.212 ± 0.010
Sep 23	00:44:37	185.42	4x900.0	490	6.6	1.66 ± 1.03	0.215 ± 0.010
Sep 25	02:02:31	185.51	4x900.0	484	6.0	0.41 ± 1.03	0.218 ± 0.010
Sep 26	02:08:31	185.56	4x900.0	489	5.8	0.53 ± 1.01	0.217 ± 0.010
Sep 27	01:33:44	185.61	4x900.0	523	5.7	-0.97 ± 0.95	0.217 ± 0.009
Sep 28	02:54:35	185.66	4x900.0	633	4.6	0.87 ± 0.76	0.214 ± 0.007
Oct 04	01:28:01	185.94	4x900.0	439	7.1	-2.03 ± 1.15	0.209 ± 0.012
Oct 05	01:43:02	185.99	4x900.0	634	4.4	-0.45 ± 0.74	0.212 ± 0.007
Oct 06	01:38:55	186.04	4x900.0	647	4.4	-0.93 ± 0.73	0.211 ± 0.007
Oct 24	01:09:50	186.89	4x900.0	488	6.4	0.49 ± 1.02	0.209 ± 0.010
Oct 24	23:18:27	186.93	4x900.0	511	5.5	-1.20 ± 0.97	0.211 ± 0.010
2019							
Jan 21	18:27:14	191.16	4x900.0	301	10.0	0.42 ± 1.67	0.210 ± 0.022
2020							
Oct 09	23:09:01	220.98	4x902.0	466	7.3	-0.84 ± 1.48	...
Nov 17	21:27:47	222.83	4x225.5	67	...	...	...
Nov 18	21:08:39	222.88	4x902.0	571	5.8	-1.91 ± 1.12	...
Nov 21	22:46:00	223.02	4x902.0	493	8.0	-0.21 ± 1.55	...
Nov 22	20:01:23	223.07	4x902.0	621	6.2	0.13 ± 1.20	...
Nov 29	20:11:41	223.40	4x902.0	545	6.6	-4.72 ± 1.28	...
Nov 30	20:06:39	223.45	4x902.0	419	7.4	-4.55 ± 1.53	...
Dec 17	18:36:43	224.25	4x902.0	580	6.5	0.05 ± 1.18	...
Dec 18	18:35:27	224.30	4x902.0	271	10.1	-1.77 ± 2.04	...
2021							
Sep 07	01:23:22	236.77	4x239.5	58	...	...	...
Sep 26	23:34:26	237.72	4x239.5	181	...	...	...
Oct 04	22:48:42	238.10	4x239.5	71	...	...	...
Oct 06	23:01:18	238.19	4x958.0	354	9.8	-2.15 ± 1.88	...
Oct 08	01:03:03	238.24	4x958.0	284	13.7	10.81 ± 2.79	...
Oct 09	00:18:09	238.29	4x958.0	334	12.1	3.50 ± 2.29	...
Oct 09	23:59:57	238.34	4x958.0	456	7.1	2.02 ± 1.47	...
Oct 11	00:32:07	238.39	4x958.0	310	11.6	-6.46 ± 2.17	...

Oct 11	23:52:07	238.43	4x958.0	483	7.8	-1.16 ± 1.48	...
Oct 12	22:15:51	238.48	4x958.0	268	11.2	-5.24 ± 2.53	...
Oct 13	22:14:39	238.52	4x958.0	458	8.1	2.31 ± 1.56	...
Oct 14	23:08:34	238.57	4x958.0	393	9.6	-4.44 ± 1.94	...
Oct 15	22:49:32	238.62	4x958.0	470	8.1	10.74 ± 1.83	...
Oct 16	22:33:41	238.67	4x958.0	339	10.6	-6.20 ± 2.00	...
Oct 18	00:49:34	238.72	4x958.0	452	8.0	-0.80 ± 1.55	...
Oct 19	23:06:57	238.81	4x958.0	316	12.5	0.45 ± 2.10	...
Oct 24	21:41:17	239.05	4x958.0	450	7.1	0.58 ± 1.42	...
2022							
Oct 10	01:59:17	255.70	4x958.0	529	6.4	-4.80 ± 1.28	...
2023							
Jan 31	18:24:14	261.10	4x958.0	522	6.9	-1.62 ± 1.36	...
Feb 01	18:00:24	261.15	4x958.0	393	8.1	5.94 ± 1.62	...
Feb 02	18:05:03	261.20	4x958.0	432	9.3	6.27 ± 1.98	...
Feb 03	18:09:11	261.25	4x958.0	480	7.1	0.56 ± 1.69	...
Feb 04	18:04:32	261.29	4x958.0	440	7.5	0.61 ± 1.62	...
Feb 05	18:12:30	261.34	4x958.0	360	9.9	-2.79 ± 1.79	...
Feb 06	18:05:48	261.39	4x239.5	172	...	...	...
Feb 09	18:15:50	261.53	4x958.0	228	14.5	6.77 ± 2.73	...
Feb 10	18:16:30	261.58	4x958.0	386	7.4	-0.38 ± 1.45	...
Feb 11	18:22:52	261.63	4x958.0	490	6.8	-1.99 ± 1.36	...
Feb 12	18:20:12	261.67	4x958.0	630	6.4	0.51 ± 1.18	...
Oct 12	21:38:56	273.19	4x958.0	311	9.0	1.24 ± 1.74	...
Dec 06	19:55:19	275.80	4x958.0	367	7.8	-1.26 ± 1.46	...
Dec 15	19:07:45	276.23	4x958.0	297	10.0	-1.64 ± 2.33	...
Dec 16	19:17:45	276.27	4x958.0	462	7.4	-2.71 ± 1.56	...
Dec 18	20:17:24	276.37	4x958.0	475	6.3	1.01 ± 1.37	...

Table D.2: Same as Table D.1 for HD 56124

Date	UT [hh:mm:ss]	n_{cyc}	t_{exp} [s]	S/N	σ_{LSD} [$10^{-5}I_c$]	B_ℓ [G]	S -index
2008							
Jan 19	21:50:15	0.00	4x800.0	425	7.7	3.13 ± 0.85	0.206 ± 0.010
Jan 21	00:46:42	0.05	4x600.0	401	7.6	1.22 ± 0.95	0.206 ± 0.011
Jan 21	21:39:48	0.10	4x900.0	559	5.2	3.85 ± 0.63	0.205 ± 0.007
Jan 22	21:24:21	0.14	4x900.0	520	5.9	2.12 ± 0.69	0.204 ± 0.008
Jan 23	21:22:30	0.19	4x900.0	501	6.1	2.44 ± 0.71	0.203 ± 0.008
Jan 25	21:27:11	0.29	4x900.0	513	5.9	3.04 ± 0.71	0.204 ± 0.008
Jan 26	21:25:53	0.34	4x900.0	549	5.1	1.33 ± 0.64	0.201 ± 0.007
Jan 27	21:43:34	0.39	4x900.0	631	4.6	2.53 ± 0.56	0.201 ± 0.006
Jan 28	23:13:29	0.44	4x900.0	307	10.0	4.40 ± 1.21	0.204 ± 0.011
Jan 29	22:01:43	0.48	4x900.0	549	5.8	0.43 ± 0.62	0.203 ± 0.007
Feb 04	21:31:58	0.77	4x900.0	603	5.0	2.03 ± 0.57	0.209 ± 0.006
Feb 05	21:35:60	0.82	4x900.0	561	5.4	2.28 ± 0.64	0.209 ± 0.007
Feb 06	22:24:25	0.87	4x900.0	650	5.1	3.42 ± 0.53	0.206 ± 0.006
Feb 09	21:45:40	1.01	4x900.0	645	4.5	2.76 ± 0.53	0.207 ± 0.006
Feb 10	20:23:40	1.06	4x900.0	665	4.1	3.26 ± 0.51	0.207 ± 0.005
Feb 11	21:50:30	1.11	4x900.0	619	5.0	1.33 ± 0.57	0.206 ± 0.006
Feb 12	21:57:10	1.16	4x900.0	606	5.0	2.58 ± 0.58	0.206 ± 0.006
Feb 13	21:50:31	1.21	4x900.0	447	6.6	1.46 ± 0.78	0.204 ± 0.009
Feb 14	22:13:45	1.26	4x900.0	583	5.0	1.99 ± 0.61	0.202 ± 0.007
Feb 15	21:51:46	1.30	4x900.0	655	4.7	0.71 ± 0.54	0.203 ± 0.006
Feb 16	21:52:53	1.35	4x900.0	627	4.5	1.53 ± 0.54	0.203 ± 0.006
2009							
Jan 30	22:19:06	18.21	4x900.0	468	6.4	1.20 ± 0.80	0.216 ± 0.010
2010							
Oct 15	03:50:12	48.27	4x900.0	688	4.3	-0.33 ± 0.49	0.225 ± 0.005

Oct 18	01:20:52	48.41	4x900.0	463	7.0	1.45 ± 0.83	0.227 ± 0.012
Nov 13	03:48:40	49.67	4x900.0	670	4.6	-2.45 ± 0.52	0.220 ± 0.006
Nov 27	04:46:08	50.35	4x900.0	614	4.8	-1.46 ± 0.58	0.224 ± 0.007
2011							
Oct 13	04:27:06	65.81	4x900.0	632	4.6	0.28 ± 0.53	0.215 ± 0.006
Nov 12	04:49:54	67.26	4x900.0	585	5.2	-2.36 ± 0.60	0.213 ± 0.007
Nov 24	04:00:21	67.84	4x900.0	495	5.8	1.41 ± 0.75	0.215 ± 0.010
Nov 25	04:52:54	67.89	4x900.0	461	6.9	-0.82 ± 0.80	0.212 ± 0.011
Nov 26	04:35:19	67.94	4x900.0	597	5.3	-0.28 ± 0.59	0.213 ± 0.007
Nov 27	04:00:24	67.98	4x900.0	470	7.1	-0.49 ± 0.79	0.210 ± 0.010
Nov 28	04:21:21	68.03	4x900.0	539	5.5	-2.50 ± 0.64	0.212 ± 0.008
Nov 29	03:54:48	68.08	4x900.0	603	4.9	-1.78 ± 0.57	0.211 ± 0.007
Nov 30	05:03:07	68.13	4x900.0	656	4.6	-2.90 ± 0.53	0.210 ± 0.006
Dec 11	03:22:05	68.66	4x900.0	615	4.5	-1.54 ± 0.56	0.213 ± 0.006
2012							
Nov 13	05:09:53	84.99	4x900.0	518	5.4	-1.40 ± 0.68	0.221 ± 0.008
Nov 20	05:10:23	85.33	4x900.0	594	5.2	0.09 ± 0.58	0.221 ± 0.007
Dec 10	05:25:60	86.30	4x900.0	658	4.7	-0.23 ± 0.54	0.220 ± 0.007
Dec 11	04:06:49	86.34	4x900.0	588	4.8	0.64 ± 0.56	0.220 ± 0.006
2017							
Oct 31	04:07:40	172.57	4x900.0	444	6.4	0.78 ± 0.76	0.239 ± 0.009
Nov 01	04:06:56	172.62	4x900.0	458	6.1	-0.17 ± 0.71	0.237 ± 0.008
Nov 02	02:42:47	172.67	4x225.0	186	...	...	...
Nov 16	03:06:18	173.34	4x900.0	433	6.5	-0.14 ± 0.75	0.236 ± 0.009
Nov 17	03:21:31	173.39	4x900.0	391	7.8	-0.11 ± 0.90	0.236 ± 0.011
Nov 18	02:48:48	173.44	4x900.0	465	5.9	-1.21 ± 0.72	0.238 ± 0.008
Nov 19	04:17:43	173.49	4x900.0	480	5.5	-0.25 ± 0.70	0.239 ± 0.008
Nov 20	03:03:31	173.54	4x900.0	476	6.0	0.60 ± 0.69	0.239 ± 0.008
Nov 21	02:54:06	173.59	4x900.0	373	8.2	-0.06 ± 0.95	0.235 ± 0.013
Nov 22	02:01:06	173.63	4x900.0	353	8.1	-0.92 ± 0.98	0.231 ± 0.013
Nov 27	04:28:49	173.88	4x900.0	465	6.4	-1.92 ± 0.74	0.226 ± 0.009
Nov 28	04:47:44	173.93	4x900.0	473	6.1	-1.08 ± 0.72	0.226 ± 0.009
Dec 05	03:05:24	174.26	4x900.0	426	7.2	-2.17 ± 0.84	0.235 ± 0.011
Dec 06	01:57:58	174.31	4x900.0	369	7.8	0.41 ± 0.93	0.238 ± 0.013
2019							
Jan 21	24:05:38	194.21	4x900.0	274	11.8	-1.32 ± 1.34	0.222 ± 0.024
Jan 27	01:35:50	194.45	4x900.0	412	6.7	-2.88 ± 0.86	0.221 ± 0.012
2020							
Mar 11	19:37:03	214.25	4x853.0	192	11.0	-2.45 ± 1.62	...
Mar 14	19:17:32	214.39	4x853.0	501	7.9	-0.74 ± 1.06	...
2021							
Jan 08	00:59:11	228.85	4x895.0	443	9.2	-2.36 ± 1.21	...
Mar 31	19:49:58	232.85	4x933.0	376	9.5	-0.16 ± 1.28	...
Apr 03	20:00:31	232.99	4x933.0	257	12.0	5.54 ± 1.71	...
Apr 04	20:00:53	233.04	4x933.0	439	8.2	-2.48 ± 1.37	...
Apr 06	20:01:05	233.14	4x933.0	326	11.7	-2.53 ± 1.85	...
Apr 07	19:55:11	233.18	4x933.0	446	7.8	1.30 ± 1.11	...
Apr 08	21:10:01	233.24	4x933.0	409	8.8	5.08 ± 1.18	...
Apr 12	21:26:43	233.43	4x933.0	337	11.2	5.25 ± 2.07	...
Apr 14	21:08:20	233.52	4x933.0	496	6.9	2.16 ± 0.99	...
Apr 18	20:58:35	233.72	4x933.0	535	7.2	3.47 ± 0.94	...
Apr 21	21:24:17	233.86	4x933.0	356	10.7	-5.58 ± 1.53	...
Nov 10	02:10:28	243.63	4x937.0	269	10.6	8.93 ± 1.69	...
Nov 12	01:53:35	243.73	4x937.0	379	9.5	3.22 ± 1.25	...
Nov 13	02:58:36	243.78	4x937.0	436	8.0	1.15 ± 1.22	...
Nov 17	01:36:59	243.97	4x937.0	348	11.1	-2.44 ± 1.65	...
Nov 18	01:32:15	244.02	4x937.0	243	14.6	0.38 ± 2.36	...
Nov 19	00:41:34	244.06	4x234.25	110	...	...	...
Nov 20	01:58:54	244.11	4x937.0	384	10.0	4.79 ± 1.36	...

Dec 14	04:13:22	245.28	4x937.0	410	7.7	-1.56 ± 1.13	...
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Table D.3: Same as Table D.1 for HD 73350. The observations from 2017 and 2018 were taken with ESPaDOnS.

Date	UT [hh:mm:ss]	n_{cyc}	t_{exp} [s]	S/N	σ_{LSD} [$10^{-5}I_c$]	B_ℓ [G]	S -index
2007							
Jan 26	23:22:43	0.00	4x600.0	410	6.9	1.76 ± 1.24	0.321 ± 0.013
Jan 27	22:24:12	0.08	4x600.0	464	6.6	-1.01 ± 1.08	0.321 ± 0.011
Jan 29	22:14:59	0.24	4x600.0	513	5.9	-2.47 ± 0.90	0.334 ± 0.009
Feb 01	22:53:24	0.49	4x600.0	350	9.1	1.24 ± 1.46	0.340 ± 0.017
Feb 02	23:23:44	0.57	4x600.0	402	7.9	4.92 ± 1.24	0.347 ± 0.012
Feb 03	22:45:36	0.65	4x600.0	563	5.2	4.67 ± 0.83	0.344 ± 0.008
Feb 04	21:59:28	0.73	4x600.0	511	6.0	1.38 ± 0.94	0.344 ± 0.009
Feb 06	22:04:25	0.89	4x900.0	465	6.9	2.70 ± 1.06	0.320 ± 0.010
Feb 08	22:20:44	1.06	4x600.0	512	6.2	0.20 ± 0.95	0.316 ± 0.009
2009							
Jan 31	01:45:02	59.91	4x600.0	462	6.8	0.44 ± 1.09	0.311 ± 0.012
2010							
Dec 12	02:00:48	115.33	4x600.0	206	15.8	5.05 ± 2.59	0.310 ± 0.029
Dec 13	03:39:28	115.42	4x600.0	562	5.5	-1.07 ± 0.85	0.306 ± 0.008
Dec 14	01:15:29	115.49	4x600.0	383	8.2	-2.26 ± 1.31	0.301 ± 0.015
Dec 19	01:04:39	115.90	4x600.0	390	7.9	2.07 ± 1.32	0.337 ± 0.015
2011							
Jan 14	01:47:07	118.02	4x600.0	229	13.2	-1.28 ± 2.23	0.339 ± 0.028
Jan 16	23:39:48	118.26	4x600.0	567	5.3	5.40 ± 0.83	0.360 ± 0.008
Jan 20	00:25:18	118.50	4x600.0	382	7.6	1.62 ± 1.26	0.318 ± 0.015
Jan 22	24:06:54	118.75	4x600.0	433	7.0	3.27 ± 1.16	0.327 ± 0.012
Jan 24	00:41:41	118.83	4x600.0	566	5.7	0.51 ± 0.86	0.333 ± 0.008
Jan 24	23:35:57	118.91	4x600.0	482	6.8	0.45 ± 0.99	0.338 ± 0.011
Jan 25	23:27:17	118.99	4x600.0	522	5.5	0.80 ± 0.86	0.341 ± 0.009
2012							
Jan 11	03:50:01	147.53	4x600.0	458	7.6	5.06 ± 1.10	0.313 ± 0.011
Jan 12	02:04:40	147.60	4x600.0	566	5.8	6.01 ± 0.89	0.301 ± 0.011
Jan 12	24:01:34	147.68	4x600.0	391	7.6	1.59 ± 1.27	0.300 ± 0.013
Jan 14	01:26:04	147.77	4x600.0	553	5.8	-0.19 ± 0.89	0.299 ± 0.008
Jan 15	01:23:37	147.85	4x600.0	570	5.6	-0.05 ± 0.83	0.301 ± 0.008
Jan 16	01:00:33	147.93	4x600.0	457	6.7	-0.39 ± 1.07	0.310 ± 0.010
Jan 17	02:27:39	148.01	4x600.0	439	7.9	0.08 ± 1.15	0.310 ± 0.011
Jan 18	01:05:18	148.09	4x600.0	543	5.9	-3.21 ± 0.89	0.311 ± 0.009
Jan 22	23:37:35	148.49	4x600.0	493	6.5	6.54 ± 1.02	0.307 ± 0.011
Jan 23	24:17:13	148.58	4x600.0	502	6.2	6.17 ± 0.99	0.304 ± 0.010
2017							
Jan 17	14:35:25	296.95	4x240.0	204	16.8	-2.08 ± 2.71	0.342 ± 0.052
2018							
Jan 07	13:59:12	325.88	4x240.0	260	11.7	-2.64 ± 1.88	0.357 ± 0.021

Table D.4: Same as Table D.1 for HD 76151. The observations from 17 January 2017, 7 January 2018, and 9 January 2018 were taken with ESPaDOnS.

Date	UT [hh:mm:ss]	n_{cyc}	t_{exp} [s]	S/N	σ_{LSD} [$10^{-5}I_c$]	B_ℓ [G]	S -index
2007							
Jan 21	24:11:22	0.00	4x500.0	352	8.4	0.48 ± 0.96	0.257 ± 0.014
Jan 26	01:15:05	0.23	4x800.0	617	5.0	-3.58 ± 0.56	0.249 ± 0.008
Jan 27	01:19:19	0.29	4x800.0	693	4.5	-3.88 ± 0.49	0.252 ± 0.007
Jan 28	01:34:57	0.35	4x800.0	761	4.2	-2.79 ± 0.43	0.253 ± 0.006

Jan 30	01:27:51	0.46	4x800.0	985	3.3	-3.74 ± 0.34	0.254 ± 0.005
Feb 02	02:05:06	0.63	4x800.0	821	4.3	-2.53 ± 0.41	0.258 ± 0.006
Feb 03	01:23:43	0.69	4x800.0	838	3.7	-2.22 ± 0.38	0.258 ± 0.005
Feb 04	01:53:09	0.75	4x800.0	698	4.8	-1.64 ± 0.48	0.259 ± 0.007
Feb 05	01:11:08	0.80	4x800.0	628	4.7	-1.22 ± 0.51	0.259 ± 0.007
Feb 15	01:54:47	1.38	4x800.0	733	4.4	-4.09 ± 0.46	0.262 ± 0.007
Feb 19	01:22:57	1.61	4x800.0	827	3.7	-2.77 ± 0.40	0.260 ± 0.005
Feb 27	23:05:09	2.12	4x800.0	436	6.9	-2.70 ± 0.81	0.262 ± 0.010
2009							
Dec 10	04:09:53	60.28	4x800.0	319	10.3	-2.49 ± 1.09	0.294 ± 0.008
Dec 11	05:29:25	60.34	4x800.0	582	4.7	-1.98 ± 0.57	0.293 ± 0.008
Dec 12	05:16:05	60.40	4x800.0	849	3.9	-1.09 ± 0.39	0.293 ± 0.005
Dec 13	05:38:30	60.46	4x800.0	459	7.1	-0.34 ± 0.75	0.295 ± 0.012
Dec 14	05:02:41	60.52	4x800.0	662	4.4	-0.57 ± 0.53	0.300 ± 0.008
Dec 15	04:12:55	60.57	4x800.0	455	7.5	0.06 ± 0.79	0.295 ± 0.012
Dec 16	03:38:30	60.63	4x800.0	799	3.3	-0.18 ± 0.41	0.293 ± 0.006
2010							
Jan 06	03:06:20	61.83	4x800.0	811	3.8	-2.01 ± 0.41	0.286 ± 0.006
Jan 23	01:47:46	62.80	4x800.0	671	4.8	-1.33 ± 0.51	0.298 ± 0.007
Jan 26	00:36:13	62.97	4x800.0	871	3.2	-2.47 ± 0.39	0.299 ± 0.005
Feb 14	02:12:49	64.06	4x800.0	509	7.3	-3.80 ± 0.76	0.279 ± 0.014
2011							
Jan 26	24:15:10	83.92	4x600.0	498	6.1	-5.38 ± 0.65	0.248 ± 0.007
2012							
Jan 12	02:58:15	103.96	4x800.0	921	3.4	-0.97 ± 0.36	0.252 ± 0.006
Jan 13	01:23:05	104.01	4x800.0	711	4.0	-0.32 ± 0.46	0.254 ± 0.006
Jan 14	02:22:10	104.07	4x800.0	851	3.5	-0.89 ± 0.39	0.256 ± 0.005
Jan 15	02:19:05	104.13	4x800.0	874	3.2	0.53 ± 0.36	0.254 ± 0.005
Jan 16	01:57:50	104.18	4x800.0	729	3.9	-0.35 ± 0.42	0.254 ± 0.006
Jan 21	24:17:47	104.52	4x800.0	610	5.1	-1.22 ± 0.55	0.255 ± 0.007
Jan 23	00:34:34	104.58	4x800.0	883	3.8	-1.66 ± 0.37	0.257 ± 0.005
Jan 24	01:15:05	104.64	4x800.0	777	3.9	-1.31 ± 0.42	0.258 ± 0.006
Jan 24	24:20:15	104.69	4x800.0	802	3.8	-1.82 ± 0.40	0.260 ± 0.005
Jan 26	01:28:42	104.75	4x800.0	799	3.9	-0.88 ± 0.41	0.263 ± 0.006
2015							
Dec 01	03:46:11	185.18	4x800.0	556	5.0	-3.56 ± 0.53	0.297 ± 0.008
Dec 04	03:53:27	185.35	4x800.0	452	7.1	-5.77 ± 0.72	0.290 ± 0.011
Dec 07	04:27:46	185.53	4x800.0	781	3.5	-5.16 ± 0.38	0.290 ± 0.005
Dec 08	03:45:35	185.58	4x800.0	570	5.1	-4.14 ± 0.56	0.289 ± 0.007
Dec 10	03:41:49	185.70	4x800.0	561	5.4	-2.99 ± 0.59	0.288 ± 0.011
Dec 11	03:32:29	185.75	4x800.0	727	3.8	-2.53 ± 0.42	0.285 ± 0.006
Dec 13	03:31:16	185.87	4x800.0	549	5.0	-1.60 ± 0.54	0.283 ± 0.007
Dec 14	04:43:52	185.93	4x800.0	193	16.8	-5.67 ± 1.90	0.282 ± 0.015
Dec 18	03:43:25	186.16	4x800.0	347	8.8	-5.22 ± 0.98	0.282 ± 0.013
Dec 19	04:21:43	186.21	4x800.0	753	3.6	-4.69 ± 0.41	0.286 ± 0.006
2016							
Jan 21	03:43:43	188.10	4x800.0	723	4.0	-6.47 ± 0.44	0.289 ± 0.006
Jan 22	02:05:10	188.16	4x800.0	617	4.9	-6.33 ± 0.52	0.291 ± 0.008
Jan 25	03:15:42	188.33	4x800.0	498	6.8	-5.45 ± 0.67	0.293 ± 0.011
Jan 27	03:17:57	188.44	4x800.0	709	4.4	-4.74 ± 0.46	0.291 ± 0.007
Dec 14	03:54:50	206.88	4x800.0	636	4.7	0.34 ± 0.50	0.288 ± 0.007
Dec 15	03:49:37	206.93	4x800.0	427	6.9	-1.67 ± 0.75	0.289 ± 0.008
Dec 18	04:11:46	207.11	4x800.0	625	4.8	-3.04 ± 0.50	0.288 ± 0.008
Dec 19	03:04:11	207.16	4x800.0	710	3.9	-3.26 ± 0.45	0.289 ± 0.007
Dec 21	03:41:23	207.28	4x800.0	473	6.1	-3.71 ± 0.70	0.286 ± 0.010
2017							
Jan 02	24:22:55	208.01	4x800.0	719	4.0	-1.15 ± 0.45	0.286 ± 0.006
Jan 07	02:02:41	208.25	4x800.0	793	3.6	-1.65 ± 0.39	0.285 ± 0.005
Jan 08	02:39:01	208.31	4x800.0	749	3.7	-2.41 ± 0.42	0.283 ± 0.006
Jan 17	14:45:14	208.85	4x240.0	266	12.8	-2.22 ± 1.35	0.214 ± 0.157

Jan 31	24:21:41	209.67	4x800.0	502	5.7	-0.71 ± 0.64	0.278 ± 0.011
Feb 15	00:29:28	210.48	4x800.0	701	4.0	-0.88 ± 0.45	0.276 ± 0.006
Feb 16	24:08:04	210.59	4x800.0	734	3.9	0.32 ± 0.43	0.279 ± 0.006
Feb 18	00:48:26	210.65	4x800.0	698	4.3	-0.28 ± 0.45	0.279 ± 0.006
Feb 18	23:40:08	210.70	4x800.0	764	3.9	-0.64 ± 0.41	0.282 ± 0.006
Feb 19	21:41:21	210.76	4x800.0	555	5.2	-0.08 ± 0.57	0.280 ± 0.007
2018							
Jan 07	15:09:20	229.17	4x240.0	372	8.3	1.77 ± 0.86	0.217 ± 0.057
Jan 09	15:55:45	229.29	4x240.0	240	12.2	1.60 ± 1.42	0.221 ± 0.126
Jan 24	04:36:58	230.12	4x800.0	261	12.1	3.31 ± 1.38	0.257 ± 0.033
Jan 29	02:29:15	230.40	4x800.0	444	7.3	1.91 ± 0.77	0.252 ± 0.015
Jan 30	01:41:42	230.46	4x800.0	485	5.9	0.61 ± 0.66	0.256 ± 0.010
Jan 31	03:08:14	230.52	4x800.0	510	5.7	1.06 ± 0.65	0.257 ± 0.010
Dec 18	02:41:28	248.89	4x800.0	358	8.4	-3.67 ± 0.92	0.267 ± 0.017
2019							
Jan 04	02:32:04	249.86	4x800.0	684	4.4	-1.73 ± 0.48	0.263 ± 0.010
Jan 05	02:47:56	249.92	4x800.0	685	4.2	-2.38 ± 0.47	0.267 ± 0.008
Jan 06	02:19:53	249.98	4x800.0	659	4.0	-0.60 ± 0.49	0.270 ± 0.007
Jan 07	02:39:45	250.03	4x800.0	711	3.9	-0.73 ± 0.46	0.268 ± 0.007
Jan 08	03:31:37	250.09	4x800.0	674	4.3	0.23 ± 0.46	0.266 ± 0.007
Jan 13	02:48:58	250.38	4x800.0	556	5.6	2.95 ± 0.59	0.259 ± 0.009
Jan 15	01:57:14	250.49	4x800.0	697	4.2	1.84 ± 0.47	0.259 ± 0.007
Jan 15	24:19:02	250.54	4x800.0	620	4.8	0.86 ± 0.51	0.260 ± 0.008
Jan 17	01:37:18	250.60	4x800.0	750	4.1	-0.88 ± 0.44	0.262 ± 0.007
Jan 22	01:13:07	250.89	4x800.0	347	8.2	-2.65 ± 0.97	0.266 ± 0.019
2020							
Mar 11	20:56:33	274.63	4x766.0	372	9.8	5.28 ± 1.23	...
Mar 14	20:21:11	274.80	4x766.0	765	4.8	-1.16 ± 0.63	...
2021							
Feb 25	01:59:26	294.68	4x196.0	222	...	...	...
Mar 22	20:49:01	296.16	4x821.0	418	9.1	-3.08 ± 1.23	...
Mar 23	21:06:05	296.21	4x821.0	526	5.9	-4.32 ± 2.17	...
Mar 24	21:34:24	296.27	4x821.0	607	6.1	-6.68 ± 0.83	...
Mar 25	21:29:09	296.33	4x205.25	134	...	...	...
Mar 27	21:21:28	296.44	4x821.0	741	4.4	-3.50 ± 0.66	...
Mar 28	21:19:43	296.50	4x821.0	729	5.4	-3.95 ± 0.71	...
Mar 29	20:50:27	296.56	4x821.0	340	9.7	0.31 ± 1.19	...
Mar 31	21:12:32	296.67	4x821.0	557	8.0	-1.07 ± 0.90	...
Apr 03	21:20:06	296.84	4x821.0	391	9.0	-2.83 ± 1.11	...
Apr 04	21:08:53	296.90	4x821.0	436	7.3	-2.77 ± 0.85	...
Apr 06	21:35:18	297.02	4x821.0	345	10.4	-0.39 ± 1.21	...
Apr 07	21:08:57	297.07	4x821.0	670	5.0	-3.40 ± 0.69	...
Apr 08	20:09:59	297.13	4x821.0	497	6.3	-1.78 ± 0.79	...
Apr 12	20:01:50	297.36	4x821.0	562	6.3	-2.40 ± 0.83	...
Apr 14	20:07:41	297.47	4x821.0	791	4.2	-5.60 ± 0.55	...
Apr 18	19:58:42	297.70	4x821.0	516	6.1	-5.19 ± 0.70	...
May 11	21:18:52	299.02	4x205.25	70	...	...	...
May 17	20:59:42	299.36	4x205.25	281	...	...	...
2022							
Jan 15	01:01:08	313.22	4x821.0	646	6.1	-2.52 ± 0.95	...
Jan 16	01:09:44	313.28	4x821.0	692	5.3	-3.84 ± 0.67	...
Jan 17	01:09:55	313.34	4x821.0	622	6.6	-4.76 ± 1.15	...
Jan 18	23:19:34	313.45	4x821.0	697	5.1	-2.57 ± 0.65	...
Jan 21	23:20:55	313.62	4x821.0	608	6.4	-2.12 ± 0.80	...
Jan 22	23:13:31	313.68	4x821.0	612	5.6	-2.52 ± 0.83	...
Jan 25	01:02:13	313.80	4x821.0	694	5.7	-4.31 ± 0.84	...
Jan 26	00:27:41	313.85	4x821.0	538	6.7	-1.52 ± 0.98	...
Jan 26	23:53:13	313.91	4x821.0	585	7.4	-2.97 ± 1.07	...
Jan 27	23:47:32	313.97	4x821.0	509	6.4	-5.42 ± 0.91	...
Jan 29	02:12:17	314.03	4x821.0	583	5.6	-0.89 ± 0.77	...

Jan 29	23:38:46	314.08	4x205.25	876	...	...	...
Jan 30	23:53:01	314.14	4x821.0	663	5.6	-1.11 ± 0.79	...
Feb 06	00:01:42	314.48	4x821.0	567	6.1	-3.38 ± 0.76	...
Feb 08	22:35:47	314.65	4x821.0	326	14.8	-4.76 ± 1.95	...
Feb 09	21:36:47	314.70	4x821.0	613	6.5	-1.04 ± 0.79	...
Feb 11	22:31:00	314.82	4x821.0	608	6.3	-1.77 ± 0.92	...
Feb 17	22:36:32	315.16	4x205.25	261	...	...	...
Feb 24	21:47:35	315.56	4x821.0	496	7.9	-2.15 ± 1.03	...
Feb 25	21:56:16	315.62	4x821.0	669	6.5	-3.99 ± 0.90	...
Feb 26	21:01:13	315.68	4x821.0	529	7.7	-3.16 ± 1.42	...
Feb 28	21:32:25	315.79	4x821.0	569	7.7	-0.71 ± 0.88	...
Mar 22	20:08:03	317.05	4x821.0	602	5.6	-2.77 ± 0.80	...
Mar 23	21:47:56	317.11	4x821.0	645	5.7	-1.97 ± 0.71	...
Mar 26	20:50:31	317.28	4x821.0	514	6.8	-1.67 ± 0.83	...
Apr 04	20:23:35	317.79	4x821.0	661	5.2	0.78 ± 0.69	...
Apr 15	20:08:04	318.42	4x821.0	588	7.0	0.06 ± 0.86	...
Apr 16	20:26:47	318.48	4x821.0	572	6.5	-1.82 ± 0.82	...
Apr 17	20:31:33	318.54	4x821.0	544	6.1	0.39 ± 0.85	...
Apr 18	20:21:52	318.59	4x821.0	674	5.1	0.06 ± 0.66	...
Dec 17	04:14:53	332.47	4x820.0	682	5.1	5.68 ± 0.68	...
2023							
Jan 30	00:03:00	334.97	4x820.0	649	5.4	6.58 ± 0.70	...
Jan 30	23:56:36	335.03	4x820.0	585	5.5	9.60 ± 0.76	...
Feb 01	00:47:08	335.09	4x820.0	799	4.2	7.91 ± 0.54	...
Feb 01	23:12:12	335.14	4x820.0	722	5.3	5.79 ± 0.64	...
Feb 03	00:17:11	335.20	4x820.0	693	4.8	6.93 ± 0.62	...
Feb 03	23:33:42	335.26	4x820.0	716	4.4	6.63 ± 0.61	...
Feb 05	00:15:51	335.32	4x820.0	749	4.7	6.91 ± 0.60	...
Feb 06	23:44:30	335.43	4x820.0	510	7.0	2.86 ± 0.93	...
Feb 09	00:44:40	335.55	4x820.0	373	8.6	4.66 ± 1.22	...
Feb 10	00:38:42	335.60	4x820.0	617	6.0	5.65 ± 0.71	...
Feb 10	23:57:19	335.66	4x820.0	781	4.7	3.72 ± 0.62	...
Feb 12	00:07:41	335.72	4x820.0	680	5.3	6.86 ± 0.59	...
Feb 12	23:34:21	335.77	4x820.0	528	6.0	8.17 ± 0.86	...
Feb 24	23:32:42	336.46	4x820.0	666	5.2	3.08 ± 0.64	...
Feb 28	22:00:34	336.69	4x205.0	258	...	...	...
2024							
Jan 10	02:35:29	354.73	4x858.0	286	12.9	3.72 ± 1.67	...
Jan 13	02:43:39	354.90	4x858.0	668	5.9	2.40 ± 0.68	...
Jan 13	21:39:25	354.95	4x858.0	383	8.9	4.16 ± 1.10	...
Jan 20	00:44:26	355.30	4x858.0	411	7.8	-1.66 ± 1.09	...
Jan 21	01:03:31	355.35	4x858.0	745	4.9	-0.46 ± 0.73	...
Jan 24	00:19:42	355.52	4x858.0	502	7.6	-0.36 ± 0.99	...
Jan 25	00:31:44	355.58	4x214.5	242	...	...	...
Jan 26	00:22:58	355.64	4x858.0	568	7.0	-0.54 ± 0.87	...
Jan 27	00:22:32	355.70	4x858.0	458	9.0	3.98 ± 1.11	...
Feb 06	23:10:08	356.32	4x858.0	368	8.3	-2.41 ± 1.13	...
Feb 17	23:51:57	356.95	4x858.0	555	5.6	1.21 ± 0.75	...

Table D.5: Same as Table D.1 for HD 166435

Date	UT [hh:mm:ss]	n_{cyc}	t_{exp} [s]	S/N	σ_{LSD} [$10^{-5}I_c$]	B_ℓ [G]	S-index
2007							
Aug 01	23:15:18	0.00	4x600.0	354	9.0	-6.74 ± 1.50	0.504 ± 0.014
2010							
Jun 06	23:45:23	298.00	4x800.0	616	5.4	5.16 ± 0.86	0.473 ± 0.008
Jun 22	00:50:59	302.31	4x800.0	567	5.8	3.79 ± 0.98	0.468 ± 0.010
Jul 01	24:11:01	305.17	4x800.0	575	5.8	2.40 ± 0.98	0.458 ± 0.010

Jul 04	23:48:52	306.02	4x800.0	690	4.2	0.81 ± 0.73	0.457 ± 0.007
Jul 05	22:48:20	306.30	4x800.0	677	4.0	0.29 ± 0.74	0.468 ± 0.007
Jul 06	23:19:21	306.59	4x800.0	711	4.3	4.03 ± 0.69	0.463 ± 0.006
Jul 10	23:18:41	307.74	4x800.0	596	5.2	7.25 ± 0.88	0.458 ± 0.008
Jul 13	23:00:27	308.59	4x800.0	578	5.4	0.78 ± 0.90	0.464 ± 0.009
Jul 23	23:15:46	311.46	4x800.0	700	4.4	3.79 ± 0.71	0.467 ± 0.007
Jul 24	23:03:31	311.75	4x800.0	669	4.3	1.40 ± 0.72	0.455 ± 0.007
Aug 02	22:47:50	314.32	4x800.0	543	5.7	3.26 ± 0.92	0.468 ± 0.009
Aug 03	22:33:39	314.60	4x800.0	696	4.6	2.45 ± 0.73	0.463 ± 0.007
Aug 05	21:11:50	315.16	4x800.0	721	4.3	2.89 ± 0.68	0.466 ± 0.006
Aug 06	20:56:54	315.45	4x800.0	599	5.1	3.66 ± 0.83	0.466 ± 0.008
Aug 07	21:26:38	315.74	4x800.0	574	5.2	4.96 ± 0.89	0.457 ± 0.009
Aug 08	21:02:26	316.02	4x800.0	577	5.2	8.75 ± 0.87	0.453 ± 0.008
Aug 09	21:42:18	316.31	4x800.0	664	4.4	2.14 ± 0.73	0.466 ± 0.007
Aug 11	21:30:22	316.88	4x1200.0	680	4.2	6.53 ± 0.75	0.454 ± 0.006
Aug 12	22:44:36	317.19	4x800.0	584	5.2	1.70 ± 0.86	0.460 ± 0.008
Aug 17	22:43:33	318.62	4x800.0	643	4.8	4.79 ± 0.80	0.465 ± 0.008
2011							
Jul 05	01:02:00	410.62	4x800.0	648	4.7	6.43 ± 0.76	0.461 ± 0.007
Jul 07	24:00:47	411.47	4x800.0	571	5.3	8.24 ± 0.91	0.460 ± 0.009
Jul 10	24:21:56	412.33	4x800.0	453	7.4	2.57 ± 1.22	0.452 ± 0.012
Jul 11	22:49:29	412.60	4x800.0	627	5.0	2.17 ± 0.82	0.459 ± 0.008
Jul 17	21:28:30	414.31	4x800.0	556	5.6	11.68 ± 0.91	0.459 ± 0.009
Jul 21	23:08:46	415.47	4x800.0	619	4.9	7.81 ± 0.84	0.455 ± 0.008
2012							
Jul 17	23:00:39	519.19	4x800.0	637	4.6	-0.27 ± 0.76	0.476 ± 0.007
Jul 18	22:47:50	519.48	4x800.0	590	5.7	-0.68 ± 0.85	0.459 ± 0.008
Jul 19	22:32:54	519.76	4x800.0	522	5.3	-0.43 ± 0.95	0.463 ± 0.009
Jul 22	22:33:23	520.62	4x800.0	587	5.1	-1.44 ± 0.85	0.451 ± 0.008
Jul 23	22:09:56	520.90	4x800.0	569	5.3	-2.89 ± 0.89	0.466 ± 0.008
Jul 24	22:39:46	521.20	4x800.0	596	4.9	-9.35 ± 0.82	0.478 ± 0.008
Jul 25	22:37:49	521.48	4x800.0	620	5.1	-3.93 ± 0.83	0.458 ± 0.008
Aug 06	20:54:52	524.90	4x800.0	629	4.4	3.81 ± 0.79	0.464 ± 0.007
Aug 07	22:06:09	525.20	4x800.0	545	5.7	11.81 ± 0.93	0.475 ± 0.009
Aug 08	20:47:57	525.47	4x800.0	602	5.2	8.32 ± 0.82	0.464 ± 0.008
2016							
Apr 07	03:19:49	908.64	4x800.0	605	4.9	-2.38 ± 0.82	0.464 ± 0.008
May 03	02:22:18	916.08	4x800.0	600	4.9	1.41 ± 0.84	0.483 ± 0.008
May 04	02:46:12	916.37	4x800.0	505	6.2	1.27 ± 1.02	0.468 ± 0.010
May 04	23:09:19	916.62	4x800.0	485	6.2	-0.56 ± 1.05	0.456 ± 0.011
May 15	22:54:24	919.77	4x800.0	478	6.4	1.40 ± 1.13	0.462 ± 0.010
May 16	23:22:49	920.06	4x800.0	341	9.1	10.42 ± 1.71	0.482 ± 0.011
May 21	00:41:19	921.22	4x800.0	487	6.3	6.77 ± 1.07	0.477 ± 0.010
May 24	00:38:47	922.08	4x800.0	520	5.5	5.84 ± 0.98	0.485 ± 0.009
Jun 03	00:33:00	924.94	4x800.0	516	5.1	-1.33 ± 0.96	0.479 ± 0.009
Jun 04	01:28:27	925.24	4x800.0	551	5.3	3.65 ± 0.90	0.490 ± 0.009
Jun 05	01:29:25	925.53	4x800.0	594	5.2	0.86 ± 0.84	0.483 ± 0.008
Jun 09	01:48:32	926.68	4x800.0	638	4.6	0.06 ± 0.75	0.479 ± 0.007
Jun 17	00:47:39	928.96	4x800.0	444	7.0	3.60 ± 1.18	0.481 ± 0.011
Jun 21	00:39:43	930.10	4x800.0	218	16.2	2.13 ± 2.58	0.475 ± 0.022
Aug 11	21:16:05	944.96	4x800.0	567	5.6	7.84 ± 0.89	0.476 ± 0.008
2017							
Apr 21	02:30:40	1017.23	4x600.0	448	6.8	0.13 ± 1.10	0.495 ± 0.011
May 08	01:04:13	1022.08	4x600.0	502	5.9	13.15 ± 0.99	0.490 ± 0.010
May 16	00:50:54	1024.37	4x600.0	388	7.6	5.45 ± 1.32	0.487 ± 0.013
Jun 01	23:58:10	1029.23	4x600.0	264	12.6	10.30 ± 2.10	0.496 ± 0.027
Jun 07	22:38:39	1030.94	4x600.0	431	7.1	9.43 ± 1.17	0.497 ± 0.012
Jun 12	22:53:00	1032.37	4x600.0	471	5.9	-0.62 ± 1.09	0.495 ± 0.011
Jun 13	23:44:41	1032.67	4x600.0	387	8.1	6.46 ± 1.32	0.501 ± 0.014
Jun 14	22:49:45	1032.95	4x600.0	474	6.3	11.51 ± 1.04	0.500 ± 0.011

Jun 19	02:29:52	1034.14	4x600.0	503	5.9	6.45 ± 1.01	0.492 ± 0.010
Jul 02	23:08:22	1038.11	4x600.0	336	8.7	13.21 ± 1.56	0.480 ± 0.017
Jul 03	23:40:39	1038.40	4x600.0	384	7.8	3.50 ± 1.32	0.482 ± 0.013
Jul 05	22:46:26	1038.96	4x600.0	453	6.7	10.50 ± 1.11	0.496 ± 0.011
Jul 06	22:35:18	1039.25	4x600.0	312	9.5	13.83 ± 1.62	0.479 ± 0.016
Jul 09	21:47:33	1040.10	4x600.0	396	8.3	12.27 ± 1.30	0.487 ± 0.014
Jul 11	22:44:06	1040.68	4x600.0	440	6.8	-7.69 ± 1.12	0.512 ± 0.011
2018							
Aug 20	22:50:59	1156.73	4x900.0	548	5.4	-2.64 ± 0.96	0.447 ± 0.011
Aug 21	21:49:35	1157.00	4x900.0	618	5.0	9.86 ± 0.80	0.456 ± 0.008
Aug 22	22:02:09	1157.29	4x900.0	597	4.8	12.86 ± 0.87	0.466 ± 0.009
Aug 23	21:47:28	1157.58	4x900.0	461	6.8	-1.13 ± 1.14	0.447 ± 0.013
Aug 26	23:04:04	1158.45	4x900.0	498	5.9	10.64 ± 1.04	0.463 ± 0.012
2020							
Jul 25	00:02:10	1358.46	4x819.0	443	8.8	5.39 ± 1.42	...
Jul 25	20:41:48	1358.71	4x819.0	303	15.3	-0.47 ± 2.70	...
Jul 26	20:42:59	1358.99	4x819.0	476	9.0	10.07 ± 1.52	...
Aug 04	21:20:16	1361.58	4x819.0	531	7.9	-2.88 ± 1.34	...
Aug 05	22:21:01	1361.88	4x819.0	375	10.6	12.56 ± 1.79	...
Aug 06	22:47:58	1362.17	4x819.0	442	10.6	7.49 ± 1.84	...
Aug 22	21:50:52	1366.74	4x819.0	498	9.2	5.88 ± 1.55	...
Aug 23	22:41:46	1367.04	4x819.0	474	8.7	6.60 ± 1.53	...
Aug 24	22:11:23	1367.32	4x819.0	486	8.5	5.97 ± 1.50	...
Aug 26	20:00:03	1367.87	4x819.0	479	8.4	10.47 ± 1.46	...
Aug 27	19:51:55	1368.15	4x819.0	513	8.4	7.87 ± 1.44	...
Aug 31	19:51:09	1369.30	4x204.75	9	...	...	...

Table D.6: Same as Table D.1 for HD 175726

Date	UT [hh:mm:ss]	n_{cyc}	t_{exp} [s]	S/N	σ_{LSD} [$10^{-5} I_c$]	B_ℓ [G]	S-index
2008							
Jul 10	21:28:54	-0.03	4x900.0	20	...	...	...
Jul 10	23:58:05	0.00	4x900.0	650	3.0	-0.85 ± 1.15	0.376 ± 0.006
Jul 11	01:01:31	0.01	4x900.0	640	3.0	-3.30 ± 1.18	0.376 ± 0.006
Jul 14	21:28:33	0.95	4x900.0	487	3.9	-0.43 ± 1.62	0.378 ± 0.010
Jul 15	21:25:20	1.19	4x900.0	534	3.5	1.76 ± 1.53	0.375 ± 0.009
Jul 17	22:21:22	1.69	4x900.0	813	2.1	7.00 ± 0.92	0.379 ± 0.005
Jul 18	00:42:45	1.71	4x900.0	796	2.1	8.65 ± 0.92	0.377 ± 0.005
Jul 18	03:08:13	1.73	4x900.0	723	2.5	9.81 ± 1.09	0.375 ± 0.007
Jul 18	21:54:14	1.92	4x900.0	802	2.2	-2.20 ± 0.96	0.376 ± 0.005
Jul 18	24:12:41	1.95	4x900.0	677	2.8	-4.96 ± 1.12	0.375 ± 0.006
Jul 19	02:44:22	1.97	4x900.0	671	3.0	-5.31 ± 1.18	0.375 ± 0.007
Jul 20	22:27:58	2.42	4x900.0	318	6.1	-5.81 ± 2.58	0.376 ± 0.014
Jul 21	00:51:56	2.44	4x900.0	694	2.5	-0.06 ± 1.10	0.375 ± 0.006
Jul 21	03:39:17	2.47	4x900.0	653	2.9	2.72 ± 1.32	0.369 ± 0.009
Jul 21	21:52:12	2.65	4x900.0	491	3.8	3.18 ± 1.61	0.373 ± 0.009
Jul 21	24:13:19	2.68	4x900.0	467	4.0	5.89 ± 1.69	0.375 ± 0.010
Jul 22	02:40:30	2.70	4x900.0	553	3.2	5.24 ± 1.43	0.376 ± 0.009
Jul 22	21:59:25	2.90	4x900.0	659	2.9	-1.20 ± 1.18	0.375 ± 0.007
Jul 22	24:18:25	2.92	4x900.0	644	2.9	-1.51 ± 1.19	0.376 ± 0.007
Jul 23	02:41:14	2.95	4x800.0	669	2.8	-1.35 ± 1.16	0.377 ± 0.007
Jul 24	22:07:41	3.39	4x900.0	740	2.4	1.01 ± 1.00	0.378 ± 0.005
Jul 25	00:32:16	3.41	4x900.0	728	2.5	0.46 ± 1.02	0.377 ± 0.006
Jul 25	02:57:13	3.43	4x900.0	527	3.6	-1.00 ± 1.57	0.375 ± 0.010
Aug 09	22:05:12	7.28	4x900.0	762	2.2	-0.05 ± 0.99	0.375 ± 0.005
Aug 09	23:08:39	7.29	4x900.0	758	2.4	1.43 ± 0.98	0.375 ± 0.005
Aug 10	22:02:31	7.52	4x900.0	702	2.5	1.01 ± 1.09	0.380 ± 0.006
Aug 13	21:34:13	8.24	4x900.0	617	2.9	3.05 ± 1.26	0.380 ± 0.007

Aug 13	22:38:06	8.25	4x900.0	671	2.8	2.94 ± 1.16	0.377 ± 0.007
Aug 17	21:52:34	9.22	4x900.0	454	4.2	1.25 ± 1.74	0.380 ± 0.011
Aug 17	22:56:00	9.23	4x900.0	500	4.0	1.36 ± 1.59	0.379 ± 0.009
Aug 18	21:25:08	9.46	4x900.0	514	3.4	-2.55 ± 1.55	0.373 ± 0.009
Aug 18	22:28:34	9.47	4x900.0	467	3.7	-4.44 ± 1.70	0.373 ± 0.010
Aug 19	21:33:46	9.70	4x900.0	693	2.7	4.58 ± 1.13	0.375 ± 0.007
Aug 19	22:37:12	9.71	4x900.0	625	3.2	8.72 ± 1.29	0.378 ± 0.008
Aug 20	21:16:14	9.94	4x900.0	722	2.3	-0.94 ± 1.04	0.384 ± 0.006
Aug 20	22:19:39	9.95	4x900.0	660	2.6	-3.77 ± 1.13	0.385 ± 0.006
Aug 23	21:28:30	10.67	4x900.0	829	2.3	0.43 ± 0.89	0.372 ± 0.005
Aug 23	22:31:56	10.69	4x900.0	812	2.2	2.15 ± 0.92	0.373 ± 0.005
Aug 24	21:52:32	10.92	4x900.0	774	2.2	-0.29 ± 0.96	0.379 ± 0.005
Aug 25	23:10:15	11.18	4x900.0	736	2.4	0.41 ± 1.02	0.378 ± 0.006
Aug 26	23:27:10	11.42	4x900.0	793	2.3	-1.86 ± 1.04	0.368 ± 0.008
2012							
Aug 16	21:51:11	364.28	4x900.0	507	3.8	0.14 ± 1.54	0.380 ± 0.008
Aug 17	22:18:12	364.53	4x900.0	525	3.4	3.71 ± 1.51	0.380 ± 0.008
Aug 18	23:03:43	364.78	4x900.0	480	3.8	-1.87 ± 1.63	0.377 ± 0.009
Aug 20	20:45:31	365.24	4x900.0	515	3.5	-3.96 ± 1.52	0.380 ± 0.008
Aug 21	21:41:44	365.49	4x900.0	638	3.1	-2.75 ± 1.19	0.380 ± 0.006
Aug 22	24:13:07	365.76	4x900.0	396	4.9	2.40 ± 2.00	0.371 ± 0.014
2016							
Jul 03	01:24:41	708.67	4x900.0	607	3.0	4.59 ± 1.25	0.358 ± 0.007
Jul 04	01:07:39	708.91	4x900.0	733	2.6	1.15 ± 1.05	0.368 ± 0.006
Jul 05	24:03:31	709.39	4x900.0	618	3.1	1.94 ± 1.28	0.351 ± 0.007
Jul 06	22:14:26	709.61	4x900.0	397	4.4	2.72 ± 2.00	0.360 ± 0.010
Jul 08	23:02:29	710.11	4x900.0	697	2.7	-1.57 ± 1.09	0.364 ± 0.006
Jul 10	01:10:06	710.37	4x900.0	688	2.6	1.11 ± 1.11	0.353 ± 0.006
Jul 13	00:33:01	711.10	4x900.0	536	3.6	-0.53 ± 1.54	0.361 ± 0.009
Jul 14	23:47:21	711.57	4x900.0	612	3.2	2.45 ± 1.26	0.355 ± 0.007
Jul 15	23:33:29	711.81	4x900.0	616	3.2	-0.15 ± 1.28	0.359 ± 0.007
Jul 18	23:17:58	712.54	4x900.0	676	2.3	4.17 ± 1.11	0.350 ± 0.006
Jul 19	21:57:38	712.77	4x900.0	627	2.8	-0.02 ± 1.27	0.362 ± 0.007
Jul 20	23:23:42	713.03	4x900.0	608	3.0	-0.02 ± 1.26	0.362 ± 0.007
Jul 25	21:49:56	714.23	4x900.0	702	2.4	4.25 ± 1.09	0.361 ± 0.006
Jul 26	22:24:38	714.48	4x900.0	647	2.7	0.57 ± 1.19	0.363 ± 0.006
Jul 27	23:44:48	714.74	4x900.0	648	2.6	1.60 ± 1.15	0.371 ± 0.006
2024							
Jun 25	00:11:19	1417.32	4x887.0	184	10.9	-1.41 ± 5.35	...
Jun 25	23:40:23	1417.55	4x887.0	208	10.3	-23.01 ± 6.20	...
Jun 28	00:10:34	1418.05	4x887.0	174	12.6	3.05 ± 6.66	...
Jul 03	00:03:43	1419.26	4x887.0	156	10.2	-13.29 ± 6.53	...
Jul 13	00:49:48	1421.70	4x887.0	169	12.9	...	...
Jul 13	23:59:55	1421.93	4x887.0	384	5.4	-6.48 ± 3.02	...
Jul 16	23:48:15	1422.66	4x887.0	370	6.3	3.33 ± 3.40	...
Jul 17	21:53:27	1422.89	4x887.0	200	8.3	-4.78 ± 4.50	...
Jul 18	21:46:16	1423.13	4x887.0	132	18.8	...	...
Jul 19	21:45:19	1423.37	4x887.0	208	9.4	-5.85 ± 5.35	...
Jul 21	21:43:27	1423.86	4x887.0	394	5.7	-0.29 ± 3.18	...
Jul 31	21:52:25	1426.29	4x887.0	394	5.6	11.47 ± 3.02	...
Aug 01	22:43:15	1426.54	4x887.0	363	5.3	-14.86 ± 3.06	...
Aug 02	22:19:54	1426.78	4x887.0	457	4.5	2.66 ± 2.68	...
Aug 03	22:11:54	1427.02	4x887.0	468	5.1	15.85 ± 2.82	...
Aug 04	22:27:11	1427.27	4x887.0	393	5.1	1.30 ± 3.10	...
Aug 05	20:30:59	1427.49	4x887.0	420	5.4	-3.28 ± 3.09	...
Aug 11	21:18:45	1428.96	4x887.0	339	6.1	10.58 ± 3.13	...
Aug 15	21:37:42	1429.94	4x887.0	336	6.6	6.38 ± 4.26	...
Aug 16	20:02:41	1430.16	4x887.0	372	4.9	-1.91 ± 2.81	...
Aug 19	20:02:18	1430.89	4x887.0	272	7.6	-6.01 ± 4.41	...
Aug 20	20:22:11	1431.14	4x887.0	291	5.6	-3.18 ± 3.03	...

Aug 21	19:54:39	1431.38	4x887.0	273	8.0	13.08 ± 4.33	...
Aug 22	19:59:11	1431.62	4x887.0	335	6.2	5.11 ± 4.11	...
Aug 23	20:04:05	1431.87	4x887.0	297	7.2	-2.16 ± 3.85	...
Aug 25	19:50:23	1432.35	4x887.0	377	5.9	10.53 ± 5.49	...
Aug 26	19:44:27	1432.59	4x887.0	383	6.0	-0.27 ± 2.95	...
Aug 28	19:36:40	1433.08	4x887.0	262	7.2	-21.38 ± 3.61	...
